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Research Article

Design and Characterization of a Herbal Tooth Gum Powder for Oral Hygiene

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ABSTRACT

An herbal tooth powder formulation was developed sometimes a blend of powdered botanicals like typically including clove, neem, turmeric, triphala are selected for antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, they study the organoleptic properties and have safety of a newly formulated tooth gum powder. Safety test it is showed no adverse effects such as swelling and redness and also irritation. The formulation has evaluation tests, like pH, moisture content, organoleptic and stability test. Menthol is used for flavoring and concentration range if 0.1-0.5%, and it is providing cooling sensation. Also, Mannitol is sweetener cooling agent and 2-10% concentration, Improved mouth feel. This qualities of product are in good quality as a natural oral hygiene product. There is a long period of safety of gum. The organoleptic analysis that the powder possesses colour, odour, texture, taste.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction discusses the serious role of oral hygiene in maintaining overall health, there is various dental problem like plaque formation, gingivitis, and periodontal diseases. Problems with commercial products are often contain synthetic ingredients that can cause adverse effects, such as irritation. There is increasing interest in developing herbal formulations that are safer, effective, and environmentally friendly product. It develops oral hygiene formulation by promoting

healthy tooth gums and by using herbal ingredients it minimizes less side effects or no adverse effect. The herbal excipients are used in non-herbal excipients for less side effect also used for a long-term safety for oral tooth gum protected from many diseases like gingivitis a mild gum inflammation, periodontitis (severe gum diseases), acute necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis.[1-4].

Herbal tooth powders and gums, prepared using natural ingredients, offer multiple therapeutic

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benefits such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant. Medicinal plants like Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), and Triphala are well known for their traditional use in maintaining oral hygiene and preventing dental infections. This project focuses on the design and characterization of a herbal tooth gum powder formulated from selected medicinal plant ingredients. The formulation aims to combine the mechanical cleansing effects of powder with therapeutic benefits of herbal extracts to provide an effective, natural, and safe oral hygiene product. The study also involves evaluation and characterization of the prepared formulation based on parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, moisture content, stability. The overall objective of this project is to develop a herbal-based oral hygiene formulation that promotes healthy gums and teeth while minimizing the side effects associated with synthetic oral care products. [3]

1.1.Types of diseases :

Gingivitis : Mild gum inflammation and most common. [1]

Periodontitis : It is severe gum disease which have destructive of stage of gum .[3]

Necrotize Ulcerative Gingivitis [NUG] : The fast bacterial infection by less hygiene.[5]

a) Gingivitis (Mild Gum Inflammation) :

Gingivitis is the most common and mildest form of gum disease. It can be reversed with proper treatment.

Cause : Accumulation of plaque and tartar (hardened plaque) at the gumline.

Location : Affects only gingival (the soft tissue surrounding the teeth.)

Symptoms : Gums become red, swollen, and bleed easily during brushing or flossing. Pain is typically minimal or absent.

b) Periodontitis (severe gum diseases) :

Periodontitis is the destructive stage of gum diseases, progressing from untreated gingivitis. It is irrepressible and requires professional intervention to manage.

Progression : The infection spreads below the gumline, causing the gums to pull away from the tooth, forming pockets(periodontal pockets).

Damage : The body's immune response, combined with bacterial toxins, starts to break down the bone and tissues that anchor the teeth.

Symptoms : Receding gums, persistent bad breath, visible spaces between teeth, loose teeth, and eventual tooth loss.

c) Acute Necrotizing Ulcerative Gingivitis (ANUG)

Often referred to as “Trench Mouth”, ANUG, is a severe, painful infection.

Cause : A rapid, aggressive bacterial infection often triggered by poor hygiene, stress, smoking, or a weakened immune system.

Symptoms : Severe, sudden pain, bleeding, and distinctive crater-like ulcers on the gum covered by a grayish film.

Treatment : Professional dental cleaning, antibiotics, pain relief and improve oral hygiene help control the infection quickly.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS :-

2.1. Materials :

The following herbal ingredients were selected based on their traditional use and documented antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and it is beneficial for oral hygiene.[1-4]

Herbal Ingredient	Botanical Name	Part Used	Therapeutic Role
Neem	Azadirachta indica	Leaves	Anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory
Clove	Syzygium aromaticum	Buds	Analgesic antiseptic
Turmeric	Curcuma longa L	Rhizome	Antimicrobial, anti-oxidant, analgesic(Pain Relief)
Triphala	- (Amalaki, Haritaki)	Fruits	Antioxidant oral cleansing

All raw materials were procured from certified Ayurvedic raw drug suppliers and authenticated by a botanist.

The following non-herbal excipients which help improves stability, texture, shelf life, and usability while keeping the product safe and effective[1,11,17]

- List of chemical excipients:-**

Chemical Excipient	Purpose / Function	Typical Concentration Range (%W/W)	Remarks
Microcrystalline cellulose(MCC)	Diluent, filter, improves flow and bulk density	5-20%	Provides free-flowing characteristics and uniform blending with herbal powders; non-reactive.
Kaolin (Light)	Mild abrasive, adsorbent	5-15%	Gently cleans teeth without scratching enamel; helps absorb toxins and impurities from gums.
Sodium Bicarbonate (NaHCO ₃)	Mild abrasive, ph. adjuster, deodorizing agent	1-5%	Neutralizes acids in the mouth, reduces halitosis, and helps maintain an alkaline environment.
Menthol Powder	Flavoring, cooling, refreshing agent	0.1-0.5%	Provides a cooling sensation and fresh breath; enhances sensory acceptability.

Sorbitol	Sweetener, humectant, moisture, stabilizer	2-5%	Prevents dryness and improves taste; helps retain slight moisture to prevent caking.
Colloidal Silicon Dioxide (Aerosil)	Glidant, anti-caking, flow enhancer	0.1-1%	Improves powder flow and prevents clumping or moisture uptake.
Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC K4M or K100M)	Mucoadhesive polymer, binder, film-forming agent	0.5-2%	Provides adhesion to gums and teeth surfaces, improving contact time and therapeutic action of herbal actives.
Mannitol	Humectant, mild sweetener, cooling agent	2-10%	Improves mouth feel and taste; provides slight sweetness without promoting dental caries.

2.2. Methodology :

The keywords we use is herbal tooth powder, neem antimicrobial activity. Also, we used to google scholar for research paper we use many articles and the references for research of herbal and non-herbal excipients and their advantages for oral herbal tooth gum powder. Also used google website like plagiarism checker for plagiarism of review paper. The overall methodology supported by references, the product as high quality save and effective for oral hygiene and common disease like gingivitis and other oral tooth gum diseases.[13]

2.3. Methods of preparation of tooth gum powder :

- a) Raw plant material was cleaned and shade-dried and grinded in fine particles.
- b) Powders were passed through #80 sieve to obtain uniform particle size. All the powders were mixed using geometric dilution to ensure uniform blending.
- c) Take the tiny amounts of chemical excipients to make exactly 20g of the herbal tooth gum powder.

- d) After taking all the excipients, chemical grind them together with the pestle until they are very fine.
- e) Now add active herbal excipients, keep mixing until the color is exactly the same through the whole bowl. Mix it very hard at least 10 to 15 minutes. And then sieve the mixed powder through mesh no.80.[1-4]

2.4. Evaluation Test

a) Organoleptic Evaluation :

- **Colour-** Colour is uniform light green to brownish yellow.
- **Odor-** It have refreshing clove and menthol scent.
- **Texture-** Fine, smooth powder with no visible large particle.
- **Taste-** It is slightly pungent (from clove) and refreshing.

b) Physicochemical Tests

- **pH Value-** Mix 1g of powder in 10ml of distilled water and use digital pH meter. The result is come between 7.9, means it is neutral

to slightly alkaline. It ensures that it is safe for tooth gum.

3. CONCLUSION :-

Herbal tooth gum powder offers a natural and gentle approach to maintaining oral health. By combining plant-based ingredients known for their cleansing, antibacterial, and soothing properties, it can help support stronger gums, reduce plaque buildup, and promote fresher breath. Unlike many synthetic products, it typically avoids harsh chemicals, making it a suitable option for those seeking a more holistic dental care routine. However, consistent use, proper oral hygiene practices, and regular dental check-ups remain essential to achieve the best results. Herbal tooth gum powder represents a traditional yet effective alternative for maintaining oral hygiene in a natural way. Its blend of herbs, minerals, and plant extracts works synergistically to clean teeth, strengthen gums, and combat harmful bacteria without relying on artificial additives. Regular use can contribute to improved gum health, reduced sensitivity, and a cleaner oral environment. Additionally, it aligns well with eco-friendly and sustainable lifestyles due to its minimal processing and biodegradable nature.

While herbal tooth powders provide multiple benefits, they should be used correctly and complemented with proper brushing techniques and routine dental visits. Overall, incorporating herbal tooth gum powder into daily oral care can be a safe, economical, and holistic choice for long-term dental wellness.

4. RESULT & DISCUSSION:-

The development of this herbal tooth gum powder was aimed at creating a natural, effective, and nonabrasive alternative to synthetic oral care products. The formulation combines traditional

Ayurvedic knowledge with modern pharmaceutical excipients to ensure stability, ease of use, and therapeutic efficacy.

The primary focus was on the synergistic effect of the four herbal components. Neem was incorporated as a potent antibacterial agent to combat plaque-forming bacteria, while Clove provides essential analgesic properties, making the powder effective for individuals with minor gum sensitivity. Turmeric acts as a natural anti-inflammatory agent, which is crucial for reducing gingival swelling. The additional of Triphala serves as an anti-oxidant, helping to tone and strengthen the gum tissue.

Unlike traditional raw powder this formulation is used microcrystalline cellulose and kaolin as the base this provide a control abrasive action that cleans the teeth surface without causing the erosion of enamel, which is very common issue with coarser powders. The inclusion of HPMC K4M(hydroxypropyl methylcellulose) is a strategic choice ; as a mucoadhesive polymer, it helps herbal active stay in contact with the gum for a longer duration after application, thereby enhancing the therapeutic effect.

The evaluation result is indicated that the powder maintains a pH of approximately 7.0 to 8.5 this is neutral to slightly alkaline range is an ideal for an oral cavity, as it helps neutralize the acidic environment created by food. The organoleptic properties are come after the formulation like the color, odor test, texture, and taste.

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